

IMPORTANCE OF USING INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH EVALUATION SYSTEM PIRLS –THE IMPORTANCE OF THE USE OF TEXTS

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Annotation: Advice on how to apply, adapt, and communicate modern research in calligraphy to students. This article discusses the PIRLS direction of the IEA and its application in calligraphy lessons.

Keywords: Handwriting, IEA, PIRLS, TIMSS, ICCS, ICILS, modern education, research, literacy, integration, speech, pedagogue.

Knowledge is the way of bright life, the light of man who has mastered science, the way of life. Perhaps both the name of humanity and its history will live through the times by science, because we will remember and revise the sciences that our great geniuses and ancestors possessed and created through their research. They are the discoveries of our ancestors who made a great contribution in the world by science. The field of pedagogy, which has been polishing and developing over time, is today bringing new ideas and new research. Many opportunities have been created to support the profession, education, creative ideas and creativity of the owners of tomorrow.

Since it is a requirement of today, we must be able to meet these requirements in every field. It is especially important to acquire modern knowledge in the field of education. One of the main tasks for teachers is to form a rhythm of oral and written

speech. The formation of written speech begins with the period of first grade literacy, writing lessons.

Nowadays request , we need to organize calligraphy lessons not only on the basis of SES(State Education Standarts) requirements, but also using international evaluation research, before using international evaluation research in handwriting classes, our teachers will have information about it, when it comes to the place.

Students and their parents should be given an understanding of this research. It is important to study foreign progressive practices to improve the quality and efficiency of education, the introduction of international standards. A vivid example of this is the practical steps in our country, the organization of international research on the assessment of the quality of education in the public education system, the establishment of cooperation with a reputable organization, such as the International Education Association for Assessment of Achievement in the field of education (IEA). The main purpose of cooperation with the IEA, which has been a leader in the comparative study of education for a little less than 60 years, is that students of the country, as well as the younger generation, can meet the requirements of research as their peers in other countries.

Since 1958, this organization has conducted more than thirty comparative studies on many topics related to the field of education. These are: Mathematics and Natural Sciences (TIMSS), Reading (PIRLS), Citizenship and Citizenship Education (ICCS), Computer and Information Technology Literacy (ICILS), etc. and generally speaking, it has been evaluating its achievements.

The research carried out by the IEA organization includes the evaluation of the academic activity of students in one or more subjects or on the basis of evaluation steps . This will help to analyze in depth the educational processes in the world in general and in each country. In the process of research, studying and analyzing the achievements of students, not all students are selected, but representatives are selected from among the students. The selected representatives will pass an objective test according to the research direction they are taking the test. The results

of these assignments will be the basis for evaluating students' knowledge. The results are not based only on the results of the objective test submitted by the students, in which questionnaires are received from school leaders: principal and deputy principal, teachers, students, and even parents. Factors and resources affecting the quality of school education are determined based on questionnaires. To what extent the educational process in the school is organized, what conditions exist for students to prepare lessons at home, because these factors are also taken into account during the evaluation process. We can talk a lot about these studies. But it would be appropriate if we think about the PIRLS study, which evaluates the reading literacy of primary classes. PIRLS is an international evaluation program for evaluating the reading comprehension level of primary school students. In other words, it is a large international assessment program that provides information on the level of development of reading comprehension skills of primary school students. In addition, PIRLS represents two broad goals of acquiring artistic experience, acquiring information, and assessing the skills of acquiring and using knowledge, which constitute the main part of the education of young students in and out of school.

PIRLS research keeps pace with the times. He improves his requirements along with time. That's why we recommend such methods as selecting words or sentences from modern research texts and writing them down to students, copying, converting from print to writing, dictation. In the second, third and fourth grades, it is recommended to select and write one sentence or a long word from the texts of PIRLS, even when organizing beautiful writing and courtesy moments. In this, the students remember the texts they are studying in the PIRLS club, which also provides interdisciplinary integration. For example: "My friend Stanley went to his dinner party, but he didn't even invite me to the party," or words like "Jeremy Ross," "Derek Munson," "Piece of Pie." The problem is that PIRLS research is taught to fourth graders. PIRLS texts can be difficult for first graders when they are teaching

grammar lessons. In such situations, we recommend that teachers select a section of the text with simple sentences and explain it to the students.

The writing and reading processes take place under physical and mental stress in the initial stages. The child digests the first problem and failure with difficulty. Therefore, physical and mental stress were also observed, which did not give the expected effect. The teacher notices and understands his mistake, but he cannot eliminate it even with the guidance of the student. In such cases, the teacher organizes various fun games to raise the student's morale and mood. These momentary physical and mental breaks moderate the child's mental stress and increase the child's mastery and acceptance of the subject. What we have said will bear fruit at that time, that all organizational and methodical work should be well prepared for the education of a primary school student, especially a first grade student

First of all, the teacher must create the necessary conditions for his student's moderate work. Preparation for this job starts in August. The teacher should check whether the assigned classroom and the desks are suitable for the work of his future students. After accepting students to school, they should be assigned to desks according to their height, sight and hearing abilities.

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